

VOICES FROM WITHIN AND VOICES FROM BELOW. WHAT ROLE FOR ANTI-PSYCHIATRY IN TIMES OF LIVED EXPERIENCE MOVEMENTS?

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Abstract

While anti-psychiatry historically advocated for patient participation in shaping psychiatric knowledge, contemporary movements and associations comprising psychiatricized individuals are increasingly critiquing anti-psychiatry. What are the reasons for this upheaval? To understand it, we will analyze how the anti-psychiatric approach, made famous in the world especially by the provocative positions of the U.S.-based Hungarian psychiatrist Thomas Szasz, has collided with the situated knowledge of psychiatricized people. After a general illustration of these movements, we will look at the critique of anti-psychiatry brought forth by Robert Chapman, prominent philosopher and activist of the Neurodiversity Movement, who analyzes the anti-psychiatric approach, criticizing what he sees as reactionary and outdated aspects, which end up maintaining the status quo rather than challenging it. Keeping the broader anti-psychiatric thought in the background, I will mainly use Franco Basaglia's thought to shore up Chapman's reflection and bring the two positions into dialogue. I will analyze the complicated relation that these movements have with the construct of psychiatric diagnosis, oscillating between the rejection of diagnostic essentialism on the one hand and the needs for somatic recognition and identification on the other, which risk moving essentialism to a different plane rather than eliminating it. This oscillation shows how Basaglia's and the anti-psychiatric legacy can still be crucial in bringing the needs of today's society into dialogue with the struggles of yesterday, this will allow us to understand what did not work about the anti-psychiatric movement and what we can hold onto today to achieve, over time, a more just psychiatric knowledge, capable of thinking against itself and never submitting to its own tools.

Keywords: Anty-psychiatry; Franco Basaglia; Lived Experience Movements; Thomas Szasz; Robert Chapman.

Non esiste libertà se non nel legame che
ci aiuta a lottare contro ciò che ci divide¹.

Franca Ongaro Basaglia

1. *Emerging voices and their discontents*

«I argue that anti-psychiatry is part of the problem, not the solution»²; with these words, Robert Chapman introduces the relationship he sees between anti-psychiatry and the current state of psychiatry. Chapman is an autistic philosopher and activist, particularly well known and appreciated by people engaged in the field of mental health and neurodivergence. The excerpt is from a book published in 2023 that contains a tight critique of anti-psychiatry, a summary of an analysis the philosopher has been pursuing for several years through interviews and blogposts. In this criticism Chapman is not alone. In another already influential book, *Health Communism*, artists and disability activists Beatrice Adler-Bolton and Artie Vierkant write: «The anti-psychiatric project was influential, but failed to deliver on any of its promised goals to patients»³.

Over the past three decades, there has been a clear shift towards prioritizing firsthand experiences among psychiatry's service users. This trend has been propelled by various forces, including initiatives within the profession, research communities, and online movements comprised of individuals who have personally engaged with psychiatry. The term “psychiatrized people” encompasses all those who have undergone psychological and psychiatric treatment, diagnosis, and care. Today, these communities are increasingly integrating into the social fabric, contributing to the creation of new knowledge about their own

¹ «There is no freedom except in the bond that helps us struggle against what divides us», my translation.

² R. CHAPMAN, *The Empire of Normality: Neurodiversity and Capitalism*, Pluto Press, London 2023, p. 18.

³ B. ADLER-BOLTON, A. VIERKANT, *Health Communism*, Verso, London - New York 2022, p. 65.

experiences. In academic circles, the emergence of Mad studies, a branch of the broader Mad Movement, reflects a growing effort to develop alternative understandings and forms of care rooted in the experiences of individuals with lived experiences of mental conditions. One of the most influential movements shaping discourse around lived experiences is the Neurodiversity Movement. Emerging in the 1990s from early support and advocacy networks formed by autistic individuals, this movement advocates for the acceptance and celebration of neurological differences. Together, these movements represent a significant shift towards centering the voices and experiences of those directly impacted by psychiatry, challenging its traditional paradigms, fostering new avenues of inquiry and support, and most importantly, they are trying to propose a novel perspective about the pathologization of different ways of being. The Neurodiversity Movement is at the forefront of this paradigm shift, claiming that conditions like autism are not pathologies but rather neurobiological differences. Figures like Chapman emerge as prominent voices within this movement, particularly in philosophical discourse.

While this trend appears to align closely with the aspirations of anti-psychiatry thinkers, who were among the first to advocate for active patient participation in treatment and knowledge-building, it's noteworthy that now that this "patients" begin to speak, they show discontent toward anti-psychiatric ideologies. Even more interestingly, considering that Chapman and Adler Bolton critique psychiatry as a system of social control subservient to the need for capital production. This view stems from the studies of Michel Foucault, who argues, in the seminal *Histoire de la Folie*⁴, that the medicalization of madness was a process designed to generate increasingly effective ways of controlling deviance. This insight was valuable to the anti-psychiatric thinking that was forming in the 1960s and was enriched and developed by the movement's leading figures, such as psychiatrist David Cooper, Ronald Laing, and, of course,

⁴ M. FOUCAULT, *Histoire de la folie à l'âge classique*, Gallimard, Paris 1972; trad. it. di M. Galzigna, *Storia della follia nell'età classica* (nuova ed.), Bur Rizzoli, Milano 2011.

Franco Basaglia. Basaglia and Franca Ongaro, in their fundamental work *L'istituzione negata*⁵, proposed an analysis of the institutional paradigm as a classist device of segregation of unduly pathologized subjects.

If the critique of the psychiatric system by psychiatrized people does not diverge all that much from the foundations of anti-psychiatry thinking – and it can be said, without fear of being wrong, that it partly originates from it – how can we explain the current turn toward anti-psychiatry?

In this essay, I will attempt to recount this shift, which could be crucial to comprehend the new dimensions of criticism, and to delve into the potential role of anti-psychiatry in the contemporary psychiatric debate, aiming to uphold its initial purpose: reinstating the dignity of the patient, thereby enabling them to advocate for themselves and actively contribute to the development of a novel concept of cure. I have decided to isolate what are the main points of theoretical criticism from Chapman, Adler Bolton, and other authors I have encountered. Considering my expertise, I have chosen to primarily delve into the philosophical and theoretical aspects of this criticism. However, these authors have also highlighted the practical shortcomings of the anti-psychiatric movement, a fundamental fact that deserves to be taken into account and should serve as the backdrop for any pondering on the topic, because all emancipatory movements must reckon with the long-term effects, they produce on the subjectivities they seek to defend. This applies as much to anti-psychiatry as it does to the new psychiatrized movements. However, this consideration cannot disregard the fact that the implementation of anti-psychiatry vision has encountered not only the limitations of its own theory, but also the precincts of an environment hostile to the profound change it was envisioning.

The points of criticism can be summarized as follows: (1) first, the issue about *epistemological positioning*, specifically the one of anti-psychiatry with respect to the epistemic power hierarchy; (2) second, the problem of *political positioning*, and, specifically, the influence of liberalist anti-psychiatric thought in Anglo-Saxon countries; and finally, (3) the

⁵ *L'istituzione negata*, a cura di F. Basaglia, Baldini&Castoldi, Milano 1968.

inquiry about the *ontology of the construct of mental illness*, that, as I will contend, is intricately linked to the critical concept of *diagnosis*, which currently stands as the focal point of a profound cultural transformation, a transformation we may want to watch closely.

2. *The epistemical positioning*

We have hinted that the idea uniting these movements it's that is crucial for psychiatrized people to speak up about their own condition, treatments, and care. However, these diverse movements may not necessarily agree on what, and which stakes are paramount in this discourse. We can find both reformist movements, which share a general goal of ameliorating the actual state of psychiatry, as well as more radical abolitionist movements. Likewise, the way these movements perceive anti-psychiatry varies, but it is generally marked by suspicion about its hierarchical position within the field.

The anti-psychiatry movement primarily originated from psychiatrists themselves. Even the most radical members, who advocated for the abolition of their own profession, were still influenced by institutional knowledge, and might have privileged of certain platforms because they held epistemic legitimacy through their scientific expertise and association with institutional and bureaucratic structures. While we can say that anti-psychiatrists were aware of this power and tried to use it precisely as leverage to change things, we can nevertheless understand why a suspicion in this regard remains. Mad activist George Reaume writes:

Yet, for all of their radicalism, this professional-led revolt against psychiatry had a degree of elitism. People in positions of power who did not experience madness themselves were telling the mad masses what was, or was not, good for them. Is this any different from mad studies?

Time will tell, and those who will do the telling should be mad people outside of the academy rather than those of us inside for it to have any meaning beyond self-justification⁶.

The intersectionality perspective regarding the emancipation of minorities, emerging in the 1990s but only beginning to gain traction as a preferred mode of discourse for emancipation, raises another issue, as discussed by Reaume: the predominantly male-centric-nature of the anti-psychiatric revolution. Franca Ongaro, who translated the Italian edition of *Asylum* of Ervin Goffman and co-authored several seminal texts with her husband Franco Basaglia, remains significantly less recognized for her contributions to the Basaglian revolution. Even when women were part of the movement, the historical context often prevented them from attaining the same prominence as their male counterparts. Additionally, it is undeniable, with the notable exception of Frantz Fanon, that anti-psychiatry was predominantly a movement led by white individuals coming from Western backgrounds.

2.1 *A dialectics that comes from within*

While it is unavoidable and crucial to acknowledge that anti-psychiatry operates at a higher level of power than psychiatrized people, it's also relevant to underline that it does not occupy the highest echelon. Psychiatrists, such as Basaglia, who serve as asylum directors, contend with a myriad of economic, political, and institutional constraints, ranging from budgetary limitations for services and staffing to interference from hostile political forces. Moreover, while psychiatrists may possess privileged expertise from an epistemological standpoint, this expertise is not their own creation; rather, it is the culmination of preceding research endeavors, often heavily bureaucratized and subject to external political

⁶ G. REAUME, *How is mad studies different from anti-psychiatry and critical psychiatry?*, in *The Routledge International Handbook of Mad Studies*, Routledge, London 2021, p. 101.

and economic pressures. Basaglia's achievements demonstrates the existence of a certain degree of maneuverability in this regard – a perilously narrow margin for individual agency, capable of producing Basaglias as well as monsters – however, this does not diminish the reality that psychiatrists inherently wield a body of knowledge that contains elements of hegemony. As Basaglia observes, «If we passively accept this mandate, [the one of psychiatry] are we not complicit in the violence of power that dictates our actions?»⁷.

The “psychiatrist” is not a unitary figure featuring homogeneous powers: the power wielded by a famous psychiatrist working mostly in the academy is extremely different from the power handled by a psychiatrist who work in a psychiatric hospital. Anti-psychiatry is, crucially, an emancipatory enterprise that the psychiatrist enacts against the power-knowledge of psychiatry as a broad disciplinary institution, Great emancipatory power can reverberate from the dialectic of a thought turning against what legitimizes its very existence. Therefore, it may be true, at least partially, that, ad Adler-Bolton writes that «The Italian psychiatric revolution consequently was not truly geared around the needs and lives of the patients themselves, but toward a relation of resistance from within the profession of psychiatry itself»⁸. But psychiatry's resistance to its own dogmas could be considered a key element in the collective process of liberation from the distortions and aberrations of the discipline. This process should be as inclusive as possible, involving not only psychiatrists and patients, but all health professionals and workers in health care facilities. Within this process, anti-psychiatric thought, with its various currents, could be considered as one voice among many: important and crucial, but neither dominant nor privileged. However, we saw that for Chapman, anti-psychiatry was part of a general trend of pathologizing difference and diminishing resources for mental health, and this will require a further enquiry.

⁷ *L'istituzione negata*, cit., p. 115, my translation.

⁸ B. ADLER-BOLTON, A. VIERKANT, *Health Communism*, cit., p. 67.

3. *The political positioning*

In his critique Chapman has a clear target: hungarian psychiatrist Thomas Szasz.

Thomas Szasz is indeed one of the world's best-known critics of psychiatry: born in Hungary, he moved to the United States in the 1940s, where he became famous for his radical and provocative positions against psychiatry. Specifically, Szasz is famous for his theory that mental illness does not exist, it is a metaphor invented in the 1800s that ended up in the medical semiotic encyclopedia for purposes of social control.

For Szasz what we commonly refer to as illness is a clearly identifiable affliction of the body, detectable with the scientific instruments⁹. A clearly recognizable physical substratum has never been detected in the case of mental illness, which according to the psychiatrist became a concept solely because it endows psychiatry's coercive practices with scientific legitimacy. What people suffer, for Szasz, are just "problem of living". This theory, which we will discuss in more detail in the next section, was met with strong resistance from the beginning. For Chapman, this position is in direct opposition to the neurodiversity paradigm because it reifies and depoliticizes an essentialist concept of "body normality", on which neuronormativity is based: «Szasz, most clearly, built his argument based on the assumption that bodily medicine dealt with objective abnormalities of the body, as if bodily normality were a timeless fact, which he then compared to a comparatively 'mythical' mental illness»¹⁰. It is for this reason that Chapman feels compelled to assert: «[A]nti-psychiatry is part of the problem, not the solution. For despite looking different on the surface, in fact, it reinforces rather than

⁹ T. SZASZ, *The Myth of Mental Illness*, in «American Psychologist», XV.2 (1960) pp. 113-118.

¹⁰ R. CHAPMAN, *The Empire of Normality*, cit., p. 81.

challenges the logics of the pathology paradigm and the broader apparatus of normality»¹¹.

The focal point of Chapman book is that neuronormativity is a set of limitations, implicit rules and subject disciplines that refer to an ideal cognitive subject for capital production. What falls outside this characterization is not captured as simply different, but as inherently pathological, through the conceptual grid provided precisely by psychiatry. According to Chapman, and this point is certainly cogent, Szasz's pronounced biologism remains perfectly adherent to this conceptual grid, rather than challenging it. Chapman captures something essential in his critique of Szasz, however, in his attempt to apply Szasz's views to the broader field of anti-psychiatry and possibly misinterpretations of his position on responsibility, Chapman appears to draw overly harsh conclusions, which I will address below.

3.1 *Freedom and responsibility*

Drawing on the analyses of Marxist psychiatrist Peter Sedgwick, Chapman identifies Szasz's rejection of the scientific legitimacy of the concept of mental illness as the core of a dangerous trajectory emerging from the psychiatrist's political views. Indeed, Szasz's political and social perspectives has strong affinities with a deep liberalist stance. While he does not oppose a minimal system of state care, in his work *Pharmacracy, Medicine, and Politics in America* he strongly advocates against the transformation of the welfare state into a therapeutic state. Instead, he favors a model of welfarism based on the free exchange of services between psychiatrist and patient. His thinking emphasizes the primacy of the individual over the collective, and his proposal for the abolition of the legal defense for insanity – whose scientific legitimacy he does not recognize – critiques the asylum institution without simultaneously

¹¹ *Ibid.*

addressing the equally necessary critique of the prison system, a viewpoint found in Basaglia and Ongaro's work.

Szasz's central concern lies in the concept of *freedom*: he ardently advocates for individual liberty and suggests a discourse on rights and responsibilities that unfolds within a paradigm where societal and environmental constraints are afforded limited attention. It comes as no surprise that scholars within the realm of disability and difference find discomfort in Szasz's framing of what he terms "problems of living". From the perspective of the social model of disability and the neurodiversity paradigm, disability arises from interactions with others and the environment, rather than from an individual's failure to take responsibility for their own "problems of living". Freedom, much like responsibility, may occur only in relation to the diverse forces shaping everyone's existence. These forces encompass aspects beyond one's control, such as racialization, physical and cognitive abilities, and social class.

The emphasis on individual responsibility and freedom, along with the rejection of the concept of mental illness and the associated welfare regime, did not alleviate suspicion regarding the political beliefs that sustained Szasz thought: «In particular, this world view underpinned Szasz's belief that people self-identified as 'mentally ill' mainly to take on a 'sick role' that allowed them to avoid taking personal responsibility for dealing with their problems in living.» On this point, I beg to differ on one point, subtle but by no means secondary. Szasz's polemic is not targeted to the subjects, but to the psychiatric institution: removes responsibility from the individual under the guise of scientific discourse, thereby depriving them of their freedom. That subjects in such de-empowerment might find relief and may seek it, is a secondary effect, which does not carry with it a moral judgment. It is dismantling the way through which knowledge and medical institutions deprive subjects of their freedom that drives Szasz's reflection against realist theories of mental illness:

My opposition to deterministic explanations of human behavior does not imply any wish to minimize the effects, which are indeed significant, of past

personal experiences. I wish only to maximize the scope of voluntaristic explanations—in other words, to reintroduce freedom, choice, and responsibility into the conceptual framework and vocabulary of psychiatry¹².

The idea that responsibility plays a crucial role in reinstating freedom for individuals experiencing mental distress is also fundamental to Basaglia's approach. According to Basaglia, freedom is attained when one can make choices and take responsibility for their existence as a personal project within the world. He contends that freedom and responsibility are inseparable; thus, he argues that the task – at one time symbolic and effective – of removing the bars on asylum windows should not fall to the psychiatrist, but rather to the patients themselves. It is the patients who must liberate themselves.

Only through responsible action and praxis individuals realize their capacity to choose a personal project and actively inhabit it, escaping the dehumanizing effects of institutionalization. In this sense, for Basaglia: «The man, determined by things, deprived of his freedom, objectified, alienated, is ready to fall into sick objectification. Psychiatry, as the study of the pathology of freedom, is therefore faced with a sick humanity even before it becomes sick»¹³. Unlike Szasz, Basaglia was inspired by Sartre's thought, positing this alienation within the internal dynamics of class discrimination integral to capitalist society.

Alienation, we could say with Mark Fisher¹⁴, operates through the individual's *responsibilization* for their own mental well-being. In framing mental distress as a “private matter”, Szasz is both a victim of societal prejudices and a persecutor, as his ideas have reinforced and legitimized these harmful ideas. However, because society unfairly places the burden of distress only on the individual, the desire for or enactment of *de-*

¹² T. SZASZ, *The Myth of Mental Illness*, cit., p. 32.

¹³ F. BASAGLIA, F. ONGARO BASAGLIA, *La maggioranza deviante: l'ideologia del controllo sociale totale*, Dalai editore, Milano 2010 p. 94.

¹⁴ Cfr. M. FISHER, *Good for Nothing*, <https://theoccupied-times.org/?p=12841>, consulted on 15/05/2024.

responsibilization by individuals can be seen as a form of resistance. Anthropologists Nancy Scheper Hughes and Margaret Lock¹⁵ propose that medical diagnoses can be utilized as tools for rejection or silent protest by marginalized classes. In this context, the clinical setting of objectified illness becomes a platform for expressing fear, anxiety, and anger, as individuals in such circumstances are not fully accountable for their condition. And this certainly happens not without risks. The question of the ontological reality of mental illness, a complex issue on the theoretical and epistemological level, and the responsibility of individuals, extends beyond a mere moralization of true or false illness. It delves into the intricacies of existence in the world, both as individuals and as marginalized subjects.

3.2 *Is antipsychiatry inherently right wing?*

While Szasz certainly did not invent the malingerer's problem, but he certainly helped legitimize it, it must be said that in Chapman's reading there is a problem of generalization and personalization. Demonstrating that Szasz's pro-capitalist perspective on psychiatry came to dominate anti-psychiatric discourse requires further examination. Notable figures in anti-psychiatry, such as Cooper, Laing, and Basaglia, along with influential thinkers like Deleuze, Guattari, Sartre, and Foucault, all espouse critical leftist ideologies, consistently opposing liberalism and the privatization of psychiatric services. While Szasz's influence, particularly in Anglo-Saxon countries, was undoubtedly significant due to his privilege of American audiences, attributing the construction of an implicitly conservative anti-psychiatric common sense solely to him, as argued by Sedgwick and Chapman, appears to be a hasty conclusion influenced by a certain Anglocentrism. Adler-Bolton summarizes

¹⁵ N. SCHEPER-HUGHES, M. LOCK, *The Mindful Body: A Prolegomenon to Future Work in Medical Anthropology*, in «Medical Anthropology Quarterly», I.1, 1987, pp. 6-41.

perfectly how the influence of right-wing thinking in anti-psychiatry harms the more collectively and socially oriented critique of other thinkers:

Many anti-psychiatrists who did not have left politics offered droves of unhelpful critique (like Szasz's theory that mental illnesses do not exist) while still couching their ideas within broader conceptual frames that are in fact helpful for left political projects (like Szasz's theory that the psychiatric treatment system is used improperly by the state as an extension of the legal system)¹⁶.

Of this attitude appears to be the perfect example. He was a useful figure within the trajectory of anti-psychiatry, boldly challenging conventions and advocating for non-coercive care, and he offered a vision of society capable of understanding differences and distress beyond medicalized frameworks. However, his idea of privatized models of mental healthcare, based on the free exchange of services among isolated individuals, is a problematic aspect of his legacy. Furthermore, his evaluations of psychiatry were often marred by a limited understanding of its epistemology and influenced by a radical Cartesianism.

Perhaps, however, in rereading Szasz, one must guard against the attitude that Foucault, in an interview discussing precisely the contradiction between Szasz's political views and theoretical positions, calls «criticism made through theoretical pox»¹⁷. The search for an essential evil, implicit when not actively hidden, in the psychiatrist thought, which would disqualify his entire theoretical framework. If much of Szasz's thought has resonated with his colleagues, it is also because he has dismantled important aspects of the systematic medicalization of human experience. With Foucault's words:

¹⁶ B. ADLER-BOLTON, A. VIERKANT, *Health Communism*, cit., p. 69.

¹⁷ M. FOUCAULT, *L'extension sociale de la norme*, (interview with P. Werner), in «Politique Hebdo», 212: Délier la folie, 4-10 mars 1976, pp. 14-16, p. 16, my translation.

I prefer to use the technique of interested plundering. Thoughts, discourses are certainly organized by systems. But one must consider these systems as internal effects of power. It is not the systematicity of a discourse that holds its truth, but on the contrary it is its possibility of dissociation, of reuse, of replantation elsewhere. [...] Szasz perfectly felt the deep resonance between the control functions of medicine, psychiatry and the state structures of control put in place since the 19th century. However, it seems to me that he is deluding himself if he believes that liberal medicine has freed itself from this, when in fact it is the extension of these same state structures, their foothold and antenna¹⁸.

Without giving him a central position, one can therefore use his thought by trying to grasp what to hold and what to criticize.

4. *Mental illness and psychiatric diagnosis: old and new challenges*

Anti-psychiatry brought two contributions. First, a seminal analysis of psychiatric social control that helped resist certain manifestations of psychiatric oppression. Second, it brought new grounds for a cultural denial of mental illness that helped provide the state with a way to save money by closing the asylums while shifting former inmates to other carceral systems¹⁹.

According to Chapman, the anti-psychiatry movement's denial of the existence of mental illness has provided additional legitimacy for states to impose restrictions on welfare assistance and reduce attention to mental health care. From a social point of view, this denial would have contributed negatively to moralization and distrust of mental illness.

Once more, Chapman appears to depict anti-psychiatry as a personal movement, and throughout his text, there is this rationale whereby prominent, but isolated figures – Galton, Quetelet, and, as we have seen, Szasz – unduly shape perspectives on and narratives of mental distress.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*.

¹⁹ R. CHAPMAN, *The Empire of Normality*, cit., p. 84.

Although it is undeniable that anti-psychiatry has denied the ontology of mental illness as it was portrayed by mainstream psychiatric thought, Szasz's ideas has consistently faced criticism, even within the anti-psychiatric account itself. A significant divergence between Szasz's perspective and that of figures such as Cooper, Laing, and to some extent, Basaglia and Ongaro, lies in Szasz's refusal to acknowledge mental illness as anything more than a "problem of living". Unlike his counterparts, Szasz does not situate these problems of living within a framework of inherent societal injustice; instead, he attributes it to a natural and inevitable disharmony inherent in human relationships. While Szasz critiques psychiatry for its efforts to control and manage the discomforts of life, he overlooks the exploration of How individual suffering is intertwined with the ways of life designed and privileged by capitalist society, a subject tackled by Cooper, Laing, and Basaglia. His approach, rooted in Foucauldian inquiry, fails to extend into an analysis of psychiatric science and its reinforcement of societal superstructures. However, the issue surpasses mere ontological debate. It is a question of values, and probably of stakes. It is predictable that when stakeholders are given the opportunity to voice their perspectives, they often introduce unexpected issues, highlighting the danger of assuming knowledge of a subordinate group's needs from an external standpoint. Specifically, the Neurodiversity Movement presents a challenge to psychiatry, and notably to antipsychiatry, in an unexpected fashion, by claiming the psychiatric diagnosis as a means for both individual and collective recognition. The concept of diagnosis, directly linked to the "reality" of mental illness, emerges as a pivotal point of contention in the ongoing discourse surrounding psychiatry.

The Neurodiversity Movement encompasses a spectrum of perspectives, yet it shares a common belief in the significance of diagnosis – not only as an assessment conducted by specialists but also as a means for individuals to recognize themselves, comprehend their life challenges, pursue treatment, and importantly, find solidarity within a community of peers. Chapman contends that diagnosis is no longer an exclusively medical tool but has been reappropriated by autistic individuals as a

form of self-empowerment and as a political assertion: «Still, the distinct utility of disability classifications largely resides in their providing the grounds for solidarity, culture, and community understood in the context of the minority disabled group»²⁰.

Psychiatric diagnoses, one of the fundamental tools of the discipline, are identity and destiny for the people who receive them. The antipsychiatric movement has been strongly critical of diagnostic categorization, seeing in the nosographic act a bracketing of the person from the abstract category of illness. This skepticism towards psychiatric diagnoses is eloquently articulated by Basaglia in *L'istituzione negata*, where he highlights the inherent risks of reducing individuals to abstract categories of illness. Basaglia's insights underscore the broader tension between the medical model of diagnosis and the holistic understanding of human experience advocated by antipsychiatric thinkers:

What this means, however, is that the sick person was isolated and bracketed by psychiatry so that we could deal with the abstract definition of an illness, the codification of forms, the classification of symptoms, without fearing any possible denials from a reality that, in this way, was being denied... The psychiatrist therefore makes use, in diagnosis, of a power, a technical terminology to sanction what society has already enacted in excluding from itself the one who has not integrated himself into the game of the system²¹.

On the last point, Basaglia and Chapman share a common ground: diagnostic classifications do not originate solely within psychiatry itself, but rather reflect existing prejudices and alienation present in society. These biases are inevitably reproduced, at least in part, by researchers and healthcare professionals who are deeply entwined with the societal context in which they operate. Psychiatry does not create these biases;

²⁰ ID., *Neurodiversity and the Biopolitics of Diagnosis* <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/neurodiverse-age/202103/neurodiversity-and-the-biopolitics-diagnosis>, consulted 15/05/2024 h. 12:00.

²¹ *L'istituzione negata*, cit., p. 70, my translation.

instead, psychiatric knowledge emerges from the interplay of common sense, resistance from organized groups, and scientific research data. This Foucauldian argument is often paired with Ian Hacking's notion of the looping effect²², which posits that psychiatric constructions both mirror dominant ideologies and undergo constant transformation through acts of resistance. However, this does not suggest that feedback occurs between equally balanced sources of power, rather, it indicates, in a Foucauldian sense, that power is always met with resistance, and power relations are not centralized or hierarchical, but distributed across a microphysics in which we all participate. Poignantly, the use of Foucault here serves to further cast doubt on Hacking and Chapman's positions, suggesting that while minority groups undoubtedly resist hegemony, they also risk perpetuating it in their own practices and narratives.

Medicalization, as expounded by Foucault and anti-psychiatric discourse – particularly by Szasz himself – is a pervasive process of normalizing subjectivities through biological and medical frameworks. While neurodiversity discourse aims to shield itself from becoming a conduit for a new type of medicalization rooted in cerebral and biological essentialism, some oscillations suggest that this endeavor will be challenging.

4.1 *Difference, disorder, identity*

The basic point from which the Neurodiversity Movement starts is that autism, along with ADHD and other conditions, defines people who share a neurobiological and genetic difference. They share difficulties and limitations in the social environment due to a society that was not designed for the way they approach sociality, work and the environment. The difference is cognitive, genetic, congenital. But disability, according to the social model, arises in interaction with an environment unprepared for difference. What then, according to Chapman, is the difference between a neurodiversity condition and a pathological

²² I. HACKING, *Kinds of People: Moving Targets*, in «Proceedings of the British Academy», CLI, pp. 285-317.

condition, a mental illness? On this point, Chapman is understandably very cautious. In an article published in 2019²³, he argues that a mental disorder is something that is harmful to the person or those around them, caused by a hostile environment, which may or may not have a genetic root. A neurobiological difference, on the other hand, is innate, but manifests itself in and through the social: an unfavorable environment, that is, one that is not designed to meet the needs of that neurotype, will expose the difference, while a favorable environment may hide it even for a lifetime. So disability is a kind of emergent property, but neurodiversity is not; it is inherent in cognitive functioning. However, Chapman argues, if a neurotypical person has an accident that changes his or her brain functioning and, because of that, encounters all the difficulties of an autistic person in life, it makes complete sense for him or her to identify as autistic, suggesting that neurodiversity doesn't need be innate. But this identification cannot simply come through biological difference: there are disorders of probable genetic etiology – Chapman gives the example of anorexia – that cannot be called differences, because they are harmful to the subjects for those close to them; they are therefore real disorders.

In the way he deals with the issue, there is a certain confusion of different levels: that of innate, essential difference and that of identification, subsequent and contingent. But also, that of neurological difference, which at first seems to play a central, defining role, only to end up appearing entirely incidental. This confusion persists, I think, even in his most recent work, which moves in the direction of new conceptions of neurodivergence, an umbrella term - not a medical one - intended to lump together all people whose functioning does not conform to the dominant ideology of how a person should be and act.

Chapman makes the clear assertion that these concepts are now partly independent of their own medical-scientific validity because they

²³ R. CHAPMAN, *Mental Disorder within the Neurodiversity Paradigm*, <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/neurodiverse-age/201907/mental-disorder-within-the-neurodiversity-paradigm>, consulted on 15/05/2024.

are primarily political identities, but the biological, neurological basis of the discourse seems an ineradicable residue in the very way this identity is presented. The movement's vocabulary remains strongly centered on cerebral difference, so much so that Ortega recounts how neurodiversity brings into play a new way of constructing subjects through a somatic identification that creates the anthropological figure of the "cerebral subject"²⁴. This focus on the neurological and biological aspects of difference is another strong point of contrast with antipsychiatry, which has tended to prefer to see mental distress in its phenomenal and social manifestation, trying to avoid the reification of the disorder and the compartmentalization of the individual into its parts. In my opinion, however, the breaking point does not really lie in realism or relativism about mental illness. Basaglia, like other colleagues, did not argue that mental illness did not exist, nor that biology did not play a role in its constitution. His phenomenological stance led him to see the living being as a synolus of lived body and biological body, and subjects as immediately and inseparably situated in an environment and a network of relations, limits and possibilities. The difference, in my view, lies in Basaglia's and anti-psychiatry's rejection of biological determinism and essentialism, but more importantly of psychiatry's need and claim to define human types according to these categorical grids.

4.2 *The issue about needs*

From a psycho-diagnostic point of view, neurodivergences are currently only recognized through behavioral markers. This means that it is virtually impossible to distinguish who is neurotypical and who is not based on "innate" characteristics, assuming that this innate/environmental and biological/social distinction is one that we still want to maintain in our psychological sciences. I find Chapman's attempt to break out of this impasse through the Sartrean concept of "serial

²⁴ F. ORTEGA, *The cerebral subject and the challenge of neurodiversity*, in «Bio-Societies» IV.4, 2009, pp. 425-445.

collective” very interesting: autistic people are not a group defined by a medical diagnosis or by a particular type of brain: they are people who happen to share the same needs and limitations in current society²⁵. I find this approach noteworthy because of its capacity to unite individuals through shared necessities and a collective project of emancipation. However, it prompts one to question the rationale behind retaining the suffix “neuro”, as well as a terminology inherently linked to cognitive processes, and the advocacy for diagnoses as an indispensable facet of therapeutic intervention.

There is a sense that, once again, the essentialism that had been bracketed off in an attempt to disentangle identity politics from ideology and biomedical authority remains, ambiguously and never fully addressed, at the basis of the theory. Chapman is certainly right, when says that diagnosis is an immediate way for people to recognize themselves as part of a collectivity, but his conclusion that this can become the emancipatory means of creating more communal care is open to more than one doubt. Indeed, one might consider whether there are alternative avenues to foster collective unity without relying on one of the most contentious and ideologically charged tools within psychiatry. An instrument that, even if emancipated from the authority of the diagnostician who confers it – as is attempted through the practice of self-diagnosis – remains deeply entangled in the meshes of the machine of creation and legitimization of psychiatric knowledge. But it could be argued, with good reason, that diagnoses hold significance for another critical reason, one that is exceedingly practical and urgent: facilitating access to services.

For that matter, many patients did (and still do) find it helpful to see their psychological problems as mental illness or disability. Many also found state and professional support useful – yet all this would be undermined if Szasz’s views became widely accepted²⁶.

²⁵ R. CHAPMAN, *The Empire of Normality*, cit., 147.

²⁶ Ivi, p. 73.

In this respect, it can be argued that anti-psychiatry has provided a fundamental answer: that access to services should not depend on diagnostic categorization. That *needs* should come before the *classification* of human types, in the creation of knowledge, as in the allocation of resources. In the demands of the Neurodiversity Movement, there is clearly a laudable pragmatic intent aimed at solving a *hic et nunc* problem. It is crucial, however, to examine the implications of this collision between recognition needs, nosographic-descriptive categorisations, and neurobiological descriptions of human difference. Situating the legitimacy of claims in a neurotype-based identity risks implicitly endorsing the essentialism and bio-neurological determinism that dominates the mind sciences in recent years. Especially regarding the “brain or blame” disposition that is becoming increasingly widespread in the sciences of the mind and in common sense, whereby any affliction that can be traced back to the body, in the Cartesian sense, is seen as inevitable, more real and acceptable than afflictions for which a precise somatic cause has not been detected. The depathologization of this kind of somatic identity, defined as a source of pride or at least positive feelings, could ground even more prejudice toward conditions for which an explicit neurological cause has not been found. This would not, of course, be the direct responsibility of the advocates, but it is a significant side effect to be considered, because diagnosis is a concept dense with history and, crucially, moralizations. If the prevailing narrative suggests that individuals with neurological conditions are fundamentally distinct from those with psychological conditions, there’s a danger of deepening the existing disparities in treatment and moral judgment. The risk is to make neurobiological essentialism the only “safe space” for legitimizing mental distress.

Upon closer scrutiny, the potential risk lies in how the discourse of neurodiversity, rather than inserting an intermediary node between the conventional binary of normal and pathological states – a node with the capacity to disrupt this opposition from within – could end up adding a

new layer of nuance to the definition of normalcy. Anti-psychiatry's critique of the excessive use of diagnostic labels, therefore, remains not only valid, but could provide a fruitful counterbalance to the discussion. At the midpoint of the dispute, it's likely that we'll witness the emergence of a new and productive discourse concerning the needs of psychiatricized people, including those, very valid ones, that underlie the symbolic and aggregative need of a shared identity.

5. To conclude: between science and justice

Ecco appunto l'antipsichiatria. Nemica della sobrietà, lontana mille miglia dalle cautele del modo scientifico di indagare, sembra che l'antipsichiatria abbia bisogno, per crescere, di un terreno culturale in cui non si rifugge dalla retorica²⁷.
Giovanni Jervis

Anti-psychiatry has been controversial terrain for its own protagonists, who often, like Basaglia, Szasz, and Giovanni Jervis – who opens this paragraph – struggled to recognize themselves as protagonists of the very countercultural movement they had shaped. As we read from Jervis' excerpt, the need to find a middle ground between the scientific foundation of the discipline and the human understanding of the patient has always been a central point of contention in the history of psychiatry and antipsychiatry. And unsurprisingly, it is an issue connected with the role of political stances in psychiatry, with proponents of strictly scientific approach tending to eschew the idea that psychiatry is also a way of seeing and thinking about society and politics, advocating for the neutrality attributed to the hard sciences, and those who argue that treating humans is inseparable from treating the society in which they live. Between these two extremes there has been no shortage of attempts at

²⁷ «This is precisely what anti-psychiatry is. Enemy of sobriety, a thousand miles away from the caution of the scientific way of investigating, it seems that anti-psychiatry needs, to flourish, a cultural environment where it does not shy away from rhetoric». My translation.

compromise, in psychiatry as in antipsychiatry, and we can say that certainly Basaglia represented an important attempt to cure society while curing the body, to deal with politics as well as biology, and above all to overcome, and to *unthink*, this untenable divide.

Although this has always been a central aspect of the critique of psychiatric knowledge, we cannot say that we have really succeeded in finding “the subject” between nature and culture, individuality and environment, body and mind, or the psyche between the brain and the soul. With the extraordinary and encouraging progress in neuroscience, which has thrilled research and common sense in the last century, the bar has shifted back to the scientific – and sometimes scientific – side, preferring a way of thinking of people as machines subject to impulses, stimuli and with precise ways of functioning. The spiritualist, naively enthusiastic drifts on mental illness of the antipsychiatric period were perhaps guilty of leaving a flatly provocative idea of what could be a rethinking of psychiatric knowledge in a political sense. A fundamental and valuable aspect of Chapman’s text is that it recognizes how capitalism can bend in its own direction even the most hostile counter-cultural movements, as anti-psychiatry has sometimes been. It is therefore extremely useful today to ask oneself, from the point of view of the users, what went wrong with anti-psychiatry, a movement that today seems unable to make much of a difference, even within its own professional field. However, as I have briefly tried to illustrate in this essay, anti-psychiatry has been, and could still be, something more than just one of the many naive afflatuses that animated the contestation and then been absorbed into the capitalist system as harmless, reassuring counter-discourses. Anti-psychiatry can still be a movement of internal dialectics, the necessary, vital negative of psychiatry. In order to do so, it can only look at the demands of the new movements of people who have firsthand experience, accepting to place itself as a point of view, not central and no more authoritarian than others, of a movement in which the protagonists are the autistics, the Mad, the psychiatrized. Again, with Basaglia: it is the patients who must free themselves from the bars of the

asylum. Today, we might want to say: only psychiatrized people can reimagine cure.

Psychiatry is perhaps the quintessential knowledge-power, able to enact basically uncontested techniques of self-construction and everyday practices of privatization of mental distress. In the oscillation between science and political engagement, psychiatry tends toward the scientific side, presenting itself as a neutral discipline of selves, interested in the good of increasingly cerebral, isolated subjects parceled out into somatic functioning. The problem that many anti-psychiatrists had warned of, when they railed against this de-politization of human pain, was how hegemony can use science to legitimize and reproduce itself through the relief that sells to the citizens. Science finds itself, in every sphere, in this ambivalent position, because it legitimizes, in a defining way, practices and limitations in a claimed neutrality and impartiality, concealing the forces of power that constitute it. In this ambivalence, however, lies the fundamental counterbalance that Jervis, Chapman, and Basaglia, and perhaps, more naively, Szasz, saw in it: the fact that science has been, is, and can be, an important part of the emancipation of subjects, not only because it gives the means to explain and understand, but precisely because those means are immediately legitimized in our scientific image of the world. The power of science, that of legitimizing discourses in society broadly, is thus like all powers, dual and ambiguous. It can be used to take away freedom as well as to give it. It is a human product, sometimes too human, and therefore subservient to the meshes of capital, accumulation and exploitation. Here lies the need for the countervailing leverage of anti-psychiatry: to be an opposing force, a necessary resistance, part of the broad effort in monitoring the long-term effects of counter-narratives. That is precisely because it stands in a middle ground, between scientific expertise and human pain, the person, the injustice of reified deviance. We have tried to illustrate how even within the discourse of neurodiversity there might be hidden “master’s tools” that can escape our control. The idea that ontological discourse on mental disorders should always be viewed with suspicion, and that scientific endeavors should be monitored in both their methods

and results, never taken as definitive but always subject to negotiation with suspicion and praxis, is more fundamental today than ever before. Anti-psychiatry could be, in this regard, another standpoint that poses its own questioning: where does the disorder begin, where does the difference begin? Where do they take root, from which point do they radiate? What do they signify, what do they tell us about the society we live in? Where does the *man* begin? In their own mind, into the body, in the intricacies of their relationships? And where do they end? Within the sealed confines of the skin, within society, within the vast expanse of the world? On the other hand, as Emily Dickinson suggested: «The brain is wider than the sky».